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Leadership styles and AI acceptance in academic libraries in higher education

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the relationship between the leadership styles adopted by academic librarians and their openness to artificial intelligence (AI). The purpose was to discern whether particular leadership approaches influence librarians' attitudes and acceptance of AI technologies in higher education. Data was collected from 50 librarians across four Arab countries. Two distinct questionnaires were administered to the participants: the first focused on their perceptions of AI, exploring attitudes, beliefs, and understanding of AI technologies, while the second implemented the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ 5×) to assess the librarians' leadership styles. Correlational analysis, inferential statistics including structural equation model, and regression analysis were employed leading to explore the predictive power of various leadership styles on librarians' openness to AI. Findings suggest that the implementation of AI in academic libraries is most likely to occur under transformational leadership, with transactional leadership being associated with suboptimal outcomes; a noteworthy association is observed between the perception of ease of use and the adoption of laissez-faire leadership. The insights derived from this study hold particular significance for the development of librarians' professional training programs, offering valuable guidance on fostering adaptive leadership strategies that align with the evolving landscape of AI integration within academic library settings.

Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of higher education, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force, promising enhanced efficiency, innovation, and adaptability (Popenici & Kerr, 2017). As educational institutions grapple with the potential of AI to revolutionize academic practices, the role of academic librarians becomes increasingly pivotal (Ali et al., 2020). In fact, librarians, positioned as guardians of information, find themselves at the forefront of steering through the currents of this technological transformation within the academic domain (Owolabi et al., 2022). In their role as custodians of knowledge, librarians bear a significant responsibility in leading the way through the changes brought about by advancing technologies and the process of digitalization within the academic landscape (Wood & Evans, 2018).

Digitalization, the pervasive integration of digital technologies into various aspects of organizational functioning, is significantly facilitated by effective leadership practices (Avidov-Ungar et al., 2022). The term 'digital leadership' has emerged to encapsulate the critical role leaders

play in navigating and driving digital transformations within their respective domains (Ghamrawi & Tamim, 2023). Digital leadership goes beyond the conventional understanding of management, emphasizing a proactive approach to technology adoption, fostering a culture of innovation, and ensuring that the workforce is equipped with the necessary skills for the digital era (Avidov-Ungar et al., 2022; Ghamrawi & Tamim, 2023). Individuals who embody digital leadership recognize the strategic implications of technology and guide their organizations in harnessing its full potential (Ghamrawi et al., 2023). In essence, the success of digitalization often hinges on the vision, adaptability, and proactive strategies exhibited by those in leadership roles (Ghamrawi, 2022).

The literature suggests that leadership styles, such as transactional, transformational, and laissez-faire, play a crucial role in shaping organizational responses to change (Ghamrawi, 2013). The transactional leader emphasizes established processes and efficiency, the transformational leader inspires innovation and change, while the laissez-faire leader fosters autonomy within the team (Thanh et al., 2022). The influence of these leadership paradigms extends beyond mere

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organizational structures; it permeates individuals' attitudes, shaping perceptions, fostering acceptance of reforms, and influencing the willingness to embrace innovative ideas and technologies (Ghamrawi & Tamim, 2023).

Despite the myriad factors influencing academic librarians' inclination to embrace digitalization and advocate for the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in their work environments, it is noteworthy that leadership styles remain a relatively underexplored facet within the existing literature. While discussions often revolve around technological infrastructure, institutional policies, and individual attitudes, the impact of leadership approaches on librarians' engagement with AI has received comparatively less attention. Leadership styles play a pivotal role in shaping responses to change (Khaw et al., 2022).

Recognizing the significance of leadership in influencing the enactment of AI among academic librarians is crucial for comprehensively understanding the dynamics of AI adoption in this context. This study seeks to address this gap by meticulously examining the interplay between leadership styles and librarians' openness to AI, contributing valuable insights to the broader discourse on AI integration within academic library settings.

As such, the study was guided by the following research question: How do different leadership styles, including transactional, transformational, and laissez-faire, influence academic librarians' attitudes and openness to the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) within the rapidly evolving landscape of higher education.

Literature review

Artificial Intelligence in education

Artificial Intelligence (AI) represents a branch of computer science that endeavors to create intelligent machines capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence (Xia et al., 2022). The exponential expansion of its influence is progressively reshaping the manners in which individuals engage, communicate, lead their lives, acquire knowledge, and engage in professional activities (Chiu et al., 2022). The phenomenal growth it is experiencing is fundamentally altering the dynamics of human interaction across various aspects of life, ushering in a new era marked by transformative changes in societal, educational, and professional landscapes (Chiu, 2021).

AI in Education, encompasses the strategic application of AI technologies such as intelligent tutoring systems, chatbots, robots, and automated assessment tools across diverse digital platforms to augment and refine the educational offerings (Naccache et al., 2023; Shal et al., 2024; Xia et al., 2022). This domain holds significant promise for enhancing learning outcomes, teaching methodologies, assessment processes, and overall educational administration (Pedro et al., 2019). It facilitates the delivery of personalized and adaptive learning experiences tailored to individual student needs, provides educators with deeper insights into student learning processes, and supports real-time machine-assisted queries with immediate feedback, accessible at the convenience of learners (Xia et al., 2022). The ascendancy of AI in education signals a paradigm shift in educational practices, influencing the methods employed in teaching and learning, as well as the development and implementation of educational programs at all levels (Xia et al., 2022).

The literature suggests that AI can support student learning through task assignment based on individual competence, allowing for individualized and differentiated learning (Hirankerd & Kittisunthonphisarn, 2020; Kouatli et al., 2022). Furthermore, studies also suggest that AI facilitates human-machine conversations using chatbots that support students in honing their communication skills through continuous dialogue using a question-and-answer approach (Chew & Chua, 2020; Kim et al., 2021). AI has also been reported to provide students with prompt guidance and feedback through the analysis of their work and learning processes (Fu et al., 2020; Holstein et al., 2019). In addition, the

literature suggests that AI enhances the interactivity within digital environments (Westera et al., 2020).

Academic librarians and AI

The consideration of integrating AI into library operations, a concept dating back to at least 1985, has experienced a notable resurgence of interest in the past five years (Huang et al., 2023). Research in this domain has consistently echoed concerns about the potential displacement of traditional librarian roles by robots and intelligent agents (Pinfield et al., 2017). Despite these apprehensions, the actual implementation of AI in the library sector has progressed at a deliberate and measured pace (Cox, 2021). This measured progress can be attributed to the inherent challenges of navigating competing priorities, resource constraints, and a prudent approach towards adopting novel technologies (Huang et al., 2023). Wheatley and Hervieux (2019) propose that libraries tend to adopt emerging technologies only once they have attained a secure foothold in the market and are easily accessible to patrons through diverse channels.

Moreover, the hurdles to AI adoption in libraries are multifaceted, encompassing librarians' limited understanding of AI, difficulties in integrating AI with existing library systems and services, and the significant financial commitments associated with AI products (Li et al., 2022). A study conducted by Huang et al. (2023) explored the utilization of artificial intelligence (AI) in Chinese and British academic libraries, with a specific focus on high-ranking universities. The investigation revealed that certain institutions within this cohort incorporated AI, particularly in functionalities such as virtual assistants, resource navigation, events or lectures, and the deployment of robots. However, the level of involvement with this emerging technology varied among libraries. The overarching observation was that libraries proceeded cautiously in the adoption of AI, implementing it judiciously based on its alignment with their overarching goals. Considerations such as funding availability, the value derived, institutional support, and the expertise of librarians emerged as crucial factors influencing the decision-making process regarding AI adoption.

On the other hand, a bibliometric analysis conducted by Siddique et al. (2023) covering studies addressing academic librarianship in the Arab States between 1951 and 2021 underscore a notable upward trajectory in publications, particularly in the last four years, with the zenith observed in 2020. The research landscape in the region demonstrates a growing interest in Internet and open access, while areas such as digital libraries, research data management, green librarianship, linked data, cloud computing, library leadership, library automation, and artificial intelligence emerge as subjects warranting further exploration.

As such, the literature shows an absence of prior studies that explores the influence of leadership styles among academic librarians on their propensity to implement AI. Recognizing that a pivotal attribute of effective leadership is the capacity to take calculated risks, this unexplored terrain highlights a critical aspect in understanding the dynamics of AI adoption in academic library settings. Exploring leadership styles in the context of AI enactment by academic librarians is imperative for a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play.

Leadership and leadership styles

Leadership is the art of influencing and guiding others towards a common vision (Bass & Riggio, 2006). It is about harnessing the ability to inspire, motivate, and direct individuals or a collective towards shared goals (Bass, 1985). At its core, leadership revolves around the impact one has on others, fostering collaboration and effectively navigating challenges in the pursuit of a greater purpose (Northouse, 2021). A key aspect of leadership is the concept of leadership styles, which encapsulates the distinct approaches and behaviors that leaders employ in their interactions with followers (Yukl, 2013).

The transformational leadership style stands out as a model that

inspires and motivates followers by appealing to their higher ideals and values (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Transformational leaders articulate a compelling vision, instill passion, and encourage innovation, fostering a sense of collective purpose and commitment. In contrast, the transactional leadership style focuses on clear structures and processes, emphasizing efficiency and the achievement of established goals (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Transactional leaders employ a system of rewards and punishments to drive performance, setting expectations and ensuring that followers adhere to established standards and procedures.

On the other end of the spectrum is the laissez-faire leadership style, characterized by a hands-off approach where leaders provide a high degree of autonomy to their team members (Bass & Riggio, 2006). In this style, leaders delegate authority and decision-making, allowing followers to work independently and take initiative. While providing freedom, this approach requires self-motivated and capable individuals within the team.

Each of these leadership styles has distinct characteristics and implications for organizational dynamics (Ghamrawi, 2013). Transformational leadership inspires innovation and a shared vision, transactional leadership ensures efficiency and adherence to standards, and laissez-faire leadership offers autonomy and flexibility (Ghamrawi, 2023). The effectiveness of each style depends on the organizational context, the nature of tasks, and the needs and preferences of both leaders and followers.

Ethical considerations

In the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) within Higher Education (HE) academic libraries, ethical considerations emerge as a critical factor in shaping responsible practices. First of all, data privacy and security constitute a fundamental ethical concern, demanding stringent measures for transparent data collection, informed consent, and secure storage to safeguard sensitive information, aligning with principles of user confidentiality (Lund & Wang, 2023). In addition, bias and fairness represent another crucial ethical dimension as AI algorithms are prone to inheriting biases present in the training data, potentially leading to discriminatory outcomes. Achieving fairness in AI applications within academic libraries is imperative to uphold principles of equity and requires ongoing efforts to minimize biases and conduct regular audits of models for fairness (Hussain, 2023).

On the other hand, transparency is paramount in addressing the black-box nature of certain AI models, contributing to user trust and understanding of algorithmic decisions. Libraries must prioritize clear communication on how AI-driven recommendations are generated, fostering transparency as an ethical imperative (Fernandez, 2023). Establishing mechanisms for accountability and oversight forms a critical pillar of ethical AI use. This involves defining clear roles and responsibilities, conducting regular audits, and possibly creating ethical review boards to assess the implications of AI applications, ensuring alignment with institutional values and ethical standards (Harisanty et al., 2022). Furthermore, promoting accessibility and inclusivity is an ethical imperative, demanding that AI implementations are designed to cater to diverse user needs (Fernandez, 2023). Ethical considerations in this realm involve addressing potential disparities in access to AI-driven resources and services, actively working to bridge digital divides and ensuring that technology benefits all users equitably (Hussain, 2023).

As such, continuous ethical reflection and adaptation emerge as essential practices while adopting AI. Regular reassessment of ethical implications allows academic libraries to adapt policies and practices to emerging challenges, technological advancements, and evolving societal expectations, ensuring that their AI implementations remain ethically sound over time (Harisanty et al., 2022). In navigating these ethical considerations, HE academic libraries can potentially foster responsible AI use that aligns with their mission of supporting diverse and inclusive learning environments while upholding ethical standards within the broader context of technological integration.

Conceptual framework and hypotheses

This study is grounded in a robust theoretical framework that harmoniously integrates the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989), and leadership theories; particularly transactional, transformational, and laissez-faire leadership (Thanh et al., 2022). The TAM, pioneered by Davis in 1989, is a cornerstone in understanding technology acceptance and user behavior. It posits that an individual's intention to adopt new technology is influenced by two primary factors: perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. In the context of academic librarians and AI integration, this model enables a deep exploration of how their perceptions of the ease of using AI systems and the perceived usefulness of AI technologies interact with their leadership styles. For instance, librarians under a transformational leader who encourages innovation may find AI more useful, influencing their positive attitudes. Conversely, under a laissez-faire leader, perceptions of ease of use may vary, reflecting the autonomy within their team. This integrated framework enriches the study by providing a comprehensive lens to examine the intricate dynamics between leadership styles and academic librarians' perceptions towards AI adoption.

Two core hypotheses within the TAM assert that an individual's positive attitude towards using a new technology is influenced by perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. The result is an inclination towards technology enactment. TAM also posits that the perceived ease of use exerts influence on the perceived usefulness. This aligns intuitively with the notion that a technology's utility is heightened when it is generally more straightforward to use. As articulated by Davis (1989), 'effort saved due to improved ease of use may be redeployed, enabling a person to accomplish more work for the same effort' (p. 987). Consequently, we hypothesize that:

H1. The perceived ease of use of AI positively influences the perceived usefulness of AI.

Consistent with TAM's premise that factors influencing behavior indirectly affect perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, or their relative weights (Davis, 1989), both transactional and transformational leadership can systematically influence these factors in accordance with the theory. In the context of perceived usefulness, a transactional leader, by underscoring the advantages of a technology, perhaps by stipulating that utilizing the system is the sole means to attain specified objectives, may heighten employees' perception of its utility. This transactional leadership paradigm, with its focus on cost-effectiveness, may also underscore the practicality of a technology, particularly when introduced for considerations of cost reduction. Conversely, a transformational leadership approach, which nurtures creativity and encourages exploration, is positioned to enhance individuals' understanding of the usefulness of a technology. Accordingly, we hypothesize:

H2. Transactional leadership positively influences the perceived usefulness of AI.

H3. Transformational leadership positively influences the perceived usefulness of AI.

Concerning perceived ease of use, when a leader emphasizes adherence to assigned responsibilities and cost efficiency, reflective of a transactional leadership approach, employees adopt the technology in a structured manner to optimize both the quantity and quality of their output. Under this leadership style, experimentation and exploration of intricate features are constrained, limiting the potential complexity of the technology for individuals. Conversely, transformational leadership, characterized by encouragement of creativity and open-mindedness, acts as another mechanism shaping perceived ease of use. In such an environment, employees are more inclined to experiment with novel technologies and procedures, rapidly acquiring familiarity with features. As previous learning experiences foster latent innovativeness, the newly introduced technology is perceived as more user-friendly.

Accordingly, we hypothesize:

H4. Transactional leadership positively influences the perceived ease of use of AI.

H5. Transformational leadership positively influences the perceived ease of use of AI.

Finally, the laissez-faire approach, characterized by a hands-off, decentralized leadership style, may play a distinctive role in influencing the perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of technology. Laissez-faire leadership, by its potential in promoting autonomy among team members, allows individuals the freedom to explore and experiment with technology at their own pace and in ways that align with their preferences. This heightened autonomy may contribute to a positive perception of the ease of use of technology, as individuals can tailor their interactions with the technology to suit their unique working styles.

Furthermore, the freedom to explore features and functionalities autonomously might also enhance the perceived usefulness of technology, as individuals can discover novel and personally relevant ways to integrate the technology into their workflow. Thus, we hypothesize that:

H6. Laissez faire leadership positively influences the perceived ease of use of AI.

H7. Laissez faire leadership positively influences the perceived usefulness of AI.

The resulting conceptual model for this study is presented in Fig. 1.

Method

Research design

This study aimed to explore perceptions of academic librarians towards enacting AI, in relation to their leadership styles. The research design was grounded in the positivist paradigm, prioritizing empirical observation and scientific methods for comprehending the world (Goertzen, 2017). Accordingly, a survey methodology was employed to systematically collect data from a sample of 50 academic librarians in higher education settings.

The research instrument

This study used two surveys. The first one was the technology usage, perceived usefulness (PU), and perceived ease of use (PEOU) developed by Davis (1989). Each of PU and PEOU were measured using 6 items on a 7 points Likert scale. As per Davis (1989), the Cronbach's alpha for the PU scale is 0.97, and that of the PEOU is 0.91. The second survey used in this study was the Multi Factor Leadership Questionnaire 5x, developed by Bass and Avolio (1995). The MLQ 5x (5 times shorter) gauges essential leadership behaviors proven in previous research to correlate strongly with individual and organizational success. It is a widely used instrument designed to assess leadership styles within organizational settings, and focuses on three primary leadership styles:

transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire. The entire instrument could not be reproduced in full due to copyright. Bycio et al. (1995) provided support for the construct validity of the MLQ, while Avolio et al. (1996) assessed the content validity of the MLQ through a principal components analysis with varimax rotation.

Structural equation modeling

The researchers investigated the relationship between the two survey items in order to explore the relationship between leadership and enactment of AI. Amos 29 was used to construct the structural equation model (SEM) between the variables under investigation. The first SEM explored was the effect of the demographic on the leadership domains and the usefulness and ease of use AI, as presented in Fig. 2.

Results

Descriptive statistics are presented in Table 1, including the mean and standard deviation of the domains of leadership characteristics and enactment of AI.

Furthermore, results provide insights into the associations between demographic variables, leadership styles, and perceptions of AI, highlighting the noteworthy impact of sex and leadership styles on attitudes towards AI as shown in Table 2. Table 2 presents the maximum likelihood estimates of regression weights for various variables. Notably, the influence of sex on leadership styles is statistically significant, with transactional (-0.404, $p < 0.001$), transformational (0.791, $p = 0.004$), and laissez-faire (-0.762, $p = 0.002$) styles all exhibiting significance. Country, highest certification, and years of experience, however, do not significantly impact leadership styles. In terms of the relationship between leadership styles and perceptions towards AI, transformational leadership showed a substantial impact on both PU of AI (1.952, $p < 0.001$) and PEOU of AI (1.716, $p < 0.001$). Additionally, laissez-faire leadership significantly influences PEOU of AI (-0.411, $p < 0.001$).

Focusing on sex, as Table 3 shows, males exhibited a higher inclination towards transactional and laissez faire leadership styles, as indicated by their higher mean scores compared to females. On the other hand, females scored higher in transformational leadership, suggesting a greater inclination towards inspiring and motivating leadership approaches. In terms of AI perceptions, females showed a more positive view. They found AI to be more useful and easier to use, as reflected in their higher mean scores in both categories compared to males.

On the other hand, a regression analysis was carried out (Table 4). Table 4 shows that there was a substantial impact observed from the transformational leadership domain on both the PU and PEOU of AI. This leads to the acceptance of the hypotheses H3 and H5. Conversely, the laissez-faire leadership domain seemed to influence PEOU of AI only. This leads to the acceptance of H7 and the rejection of H6. Yet transactional leadership did not exhibit any effect on any of the PU and PEOU of AI. This leads to the rejection of both H2 and H4.

In the two regression analyses, the R² values indicated a substantial impact, with the model involving leadership domains and the utility of

Fig. 1. Theorized conceptual model of the study.

Fig. 2. Structural equation modeling 1.

Table 1
Descriptive statistics of domains.

	N	Mean	Std. deviation
Transactional	50	3.1050	0.47606
Transformational	50	2.3360	1.03613
Laissez Faire	50	1.3300	0.92367
Usefulness of AI (PU)	50	4.6700	2.02940
Ease of AI (PEOU)	50	4.6200	2.12960

AI explaining 94 % of the data, and the model pertaining to leadership domains and the ease of use of AI explaining 95 % of the data ($R^2 = 0.94$ and $R^2 = 0.95$, respectively).

To complete hypotheses testing, a linear regression was performed to test H1, and the results showed high significance (p -value < 0.001), supporting our hypothesis. Additionally, the correlation coefficient was recorded at 0.981, providing strong evidence for the substantial impact of the perceived ease of use of AI on the perceived usefulness of AI.

Table 2
Maximum likelihood Estimates Regression weights of all variables.

Variables		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Transactional	← Sex	-0.404	0.125	-3.236	.001	Sig.
Transformational	← Sex	0.791	0.278	2.842	.004	Sig.
Laissez-faire	← Sex	-0.762	0.242	-3.144	.002	Sig.
Transactional	← Country	-0.072	0.055	-1.304	.192	Non sig.
Transformational	← Country	0.122	0.123	0.991	.322	Non sig.
Laissez-faire	← Country	-0.125	0.107	-1.167	.243	Non sig.
Transactional	← Highest certification	-0.028	0.136	-0.207	.836	Non sig.
Transformational	← Highest certification	0.290	0.304	0.956	.339	Non sig.
Laissez-faire	← Highest certification	-0.318	0.265	-1.200	.230	Non sig.
Transactional	← Years of Experience	0.006	0.128	0.044	.965	Non sig.
Transformational	← Years of Experience	0.051	0.286	0.178	.858	Non sig.
Laissez-faire	← Years of Experience	-0.090	0.249	-0.362	.717	Non sig.
Usefulness_of AI	← Transactional	0.168	0.147	1.141	.254	Non sig.
Ease_of AI	← Transactional	0.151	0.148	1.023	.306	Non sig.
Usefulness_of AI	← Transformational	1.952	0.067	28.932	***	Sig.
Ease_of AI	← Transformational	1.716	0.068	25.330	***	Sig.
Usefulness_of AI	← Laissez-faire	-0.014	0.076	-0.185	.853	Non sig.
Ease_of AI	← Laissez-faire	-0.411	0.076	-5.396	***	Sig.

Thus, the model suggested by this study is presented in Fig. 3.

Notably, transformational leadership emerges as a significant predictor, positively impacting both the perceived use (PU) and perceived usefulness (PEOU) of AI. This implies that academic librarians exhibiting transformational leadership in higher education may contribute to a positive environment for AI integration, fostering both a favorable perception of its use and its practical utility. Conversely, laissez-faire leadership style demonstrates a positive influence exclusively on the perceived ease of use (PEOU) of AI. Therefore, the ease of utilizing AI appears to be catalyzed by academic librarians adopting either transformational or laissez-faire approaches. In contrast, the perceived usefulness of AI is uniquely shaped by transformational leadership, indicating that leaders inspiring innovation and motivation may play a pivotal role in shaping positive attitudes towards the practical benefits of AI within their organizations.

Table 3
Impact of sex on various variables.

	Sex	N	Mean	Std. deviation
Transactional	Male	24	3.3177	0.38656
	Female	26	2.9087	0.47244
Transformational	Male	24	1.9271	1.00553
	Female	26	2.7135	0.93022
Laissez Faire	Male	24	1.7188	0.92537
	Female	26	0.99712	0.77806
Usefulness of AI	Male	24	3.9375	1.93669
	Female	26	5.3462	1.90550
Ease of AI	Male	24	3.8403	2.06564
	Female	26	5.3397	1.95986

Discussion

This study explored the relationship between the leadership styles embraced by academic librarians and their receptiveness to artificial intelligence (AI). The primary objective was to discern the potential influence of specific leadership approaches on librarians' attitudes and acceptance of AI technologies within the realm of higher education. The findings of this study indicate that the effective implementation of AI by academic librarians is most pronounced when guided by a framework of transformational leadership. Conversely, the adoption of a transactional leadership approach appears to be associated with suboptimal outcomes in the enactment of AI initiatives. Additionally, there is a noteworthy association between the perception of ease of use and the adoption of laissez-faire leadership.

In fact, transformational leadership emerges as a significant factor influencing librarians' perceptions and willingness to embrace artificial intelligence (AI) in their professional roles. Transformational leaders, as elucidated in the literature on leadership styles (Bass & Riggio, 2006), are known for their ability to inspire, motivate, and intellectually stimulate their teams (Ghamrawi, 2010, 2013; Thanh et al., 2022). When it comes to AI enactment, this leadership style seems to be a driving force in shaping librarians' attitudes, as this study suggests. The supportive and visionary nature of transformational leaders potentially fosters an organizational culture that values innovation and embraces technological advancements, aligning with studies that highlight the importance of leadership in technology acceptance (Bass et al., 2003; Eng et al., 2023; Ghamrawi & Tamim, 2023; van Dun & Kumar, 2023; Zhu & Huang, 2023). This study suggests that librarians with transformational leadership skills are more likely to perceive AI as not only easy to use but also as a highly valuable tool in their professional toolkit.

Table 4
Regression analysis.

	Usefulness of AI				Ease of AI			
	B	t	Sig	Hyp	B	t	Sig	Hyp
Transactional	0.168	0.727	0.471	Not supported	0.151	0.652	0.518	Not supported
Transformational	1.952	10.540	<0.001	supported	1.716	9.228	<0.001	supported
Laissez Faire	-0.014	-0.076	0.940	Not supported	-0.411	-2.207	0.032	supported

On the other hand, this study highlights that transactional leadership, distinguished by its inclination towards standardized procedures, contingent rewards, and a commitment to sustaining existing operational frameworks (Rockstuhl et al., 2023), poses challenges in facilitating the integration of AI within academic libraries. The fundamental tenets of transactional leadership, emphasizing conformity and penalizing deviations from established norms, may not align seamlessly with the dynamic requirements of AI integration, as indicated by its limited influence on shaping academic librarians' PEOU and PU of AI. This finding aligns with the broader literature suggesting that transactional leadership often acts as a barrier to the adoption of new technologies in organizational contexts (Bass et al., 2003; Dhamija et al., 2023; Gutu et al., 2022).

Despite the evolving nature of academic libraries, the prevalence of transactional leadership remains prominent, even among those who express support for alternative styles such as transformational and laissez-faire, reflecting a broader organizational inertia (Maciel et al., 2018; Martin, 2016). Consequently, the implications of transactional leadership in academic libraries are significant, impeding the seamless adoption of artificial intelligence and highlighting the need for a leadership paradigm more conducive to the dynamic demands of technological integration.

Finally, this study emphasizes the role of laissez-faire leadership style in positively influencing librarians' PEOU of AI in academic libraries. Laissez-faire leadership, characterized by a hands-off approach, may contribute to a workplace culture that fosters an environment where AI tools are perceived as easy to handle. This hands-off leadership style potentially enhances librarians' perceptions of the ease of integrating AI tools into their daily workflow. However, it is noteworthy that the impact of laissez-faire leadership on the PU of AI is not parallel. Academic librarians under laissez-faire leadership may be more inclined to view AI as easy to use but not necessarily as directly useful in their work. The partial positive influence of laissez-faire leadership on AI enactment goes opposite to the literature which conceptualize it as possessing a destructive behavior (Buch et al., 2015), positively influencing technostress (Boyer-Davis, 2014), and leading to lowered organizational commitment around technology (Donkor & Zhou, 2020).

Conclusion

In our investigation, we systematically examined the interrelation between leadership styles and their perceived benefits in the specific context of AI integration within academic libraries. Throughout the

Fig. 3. Conceptual model concluded by the study.

study, our premise was grounded in the belief that understanding the perceived benefits serves as a fundamental underpinning for anticipating the practical manifestations of these leadership styles. The examination of perceived benefits was strategically undertaken to offer discerning insights, thereby contributing to the considerations essential for effective decision-making in the integration of AI technologies within higher education settings.

The study suggests that if transactional leadership styles dominate within an academic library setting, it could pose a substantial threat to the successful implementation of AI. The emphasis on standardized procedures, contingent rewards, and a preference for maintaining the status quo inherent in transactional leadership may create obstacles to the adoption of AI technologies. Such a leadership approach, focused on routine adherence and short-term goals, might hinder the library's ability to fully embrace the transformative benefits that AI offers in terms of information services, research support, and overall operational efficiency. It might impede the agility and adaptability required to navigate the complexities of a rapidly evolving technological landscape.

To facilitate the successful implementation and enactment of AI in academic libraries within higher education, a strategic recommendation is to prioritize training programs focused on transformational leadership. These programs should equip academic librarians with the skills and mindset necessary to navigate the dynamic landscape of AI integration. Transformational leadership, known for inspiring, motivating, and fostering innovation, aligns inherently with the demands of AI implementation. By investing in training that cultivates transformational leadership qualities, academic librarians can develop the capacity to inspire a culture of adaptability, creativity, and openness to change. Such training will empower leaders to guide their teams through the complexities of technological advancements, ultimately fostering a collaborative environment that maximizes potential presumed benefits of AI in enhancing information services, research support, and overall operational efficiency within academic libraries.

While the ethical considerations of AI were not explicitly addressed in this study, it is paramount to recognize their significance in the integration of AI within academic libraries. Future explorations in this domain should delve into the ethical implications associated with AI technologies, considering aspects such as privacy, bias, transparency, and overall responsible use. The successful implementation of AI in academic library settings necessitates a thorough evaluation that weighs both the benefits and potential faults. Striking a delicate balance between harnessing the transformative capabilities of AI and safeguarding ethical principles is imperative for fostering a responsible and sustainable technological landscape in higher education. As technology continues to advance, a proactive consideration of ethical dimensions will undoubtedly play a pivotal role in shaping the ethical framework of AI adoption within academic libraries.

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Informed consent

All participants in this study were informed of the purpose of the study and how data will be used. They were assured that their identities would remain anonymous across the study.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tarek Shal: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Norma Ghamrawi:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Methodology. **Hiba Naccache:** Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The author declares no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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